

Conditional Autoencoder for Parameter Estimation and Current-Voltage Curve Simulation of Perovskite Solar Cells

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Abstract

Within only a decade the power conversion efficiency of perovskite solar cells (PSCs) has increased by almost a factor of two, exceeding 26%. Easy and cheap production, together with many favourable physical properties, PSCs receive a lot of attention from the scientific community. But there are still several challenges that have to be overcome, such as improvements in device efficiency and stability. Improvements are often based on trial and error, expending time and resources without any guarantee of success. Furthermore, PSCs are still not fully understood, because their architecture is complex, and some processes cannot be measured directly. This makes it challenging to identify sources of under-performance or degradation of a device. To push the technology of PSCs to the next level, it is crucial to gain a deeper understanding of their behaviour.

We employ conditional auto-encoder to estimate device parameters like Surface recombination velocity, bulk lifetimes, carrier mobility, ionic mobility, ionic density and mobility of electron transport layer from various scan rates of current-voltage curve (JV curve).

References

[1] Zbinden, Oliver, et al. "Autoencoder for Parameter Estimation and Current-Voltage Curve Simulation of Perovskite Solar Cells.", <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-8037624/v1>

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